

METHODS OF USING VIRTUAL MODELS IN THE ORGANIZATION OF INDEPENDENT WORK IN SPECIALIZED SCHOOLS

Turakhonov Fozil Bobonazarovich

Senior teacher, Denau Institute of Entrepreneurship and Pedagogy

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6060530>

Annotation: This article discusses about methods of using virtual models in the organization of independent work in specialized schools

Keywords: method, specialized schools, interactive, laboratory, physical problem

The role of simulators in the educational process is unique, in particular, the effectiveness of the educational process is determined by the desire of teachers, students to activate their independent activities. Using the Interactive physics simulator, which we offer, the development and formation of students' aspirations, curiosity, ingenuity, the use of physics in the organization of independent learning activities, leads to great results. Some experiments can only be performed by a student in a laboratory or demonstration room. Using simulators, students will be able to model physical experiments on their personal computers and perform virtual laboratory work. Through the site <http://my.study.uz>, created by us, the student will be able to access the Internet, receive the assignment and send the completed assignment to the student's e-mail. This, in turn, leads to the development of communicative skills among students. Here's how to put one together for use with your interactive physics simulator.

Once the student has developed the skills to work in the Interactive physics simulator, it is advisable to encourage the student to model a physical process or to create a model of a physical problem and to conduct research independently. Depending on the nature of the student, the equipment in the Interactive physics simulator can be provided in advance or offered to perform independently without giving at all.

When a student is given a task of this type, he or she will need to independently model a physical process, enter the physical quantities involved in the physical process, and select objects and objects. The student is completely independent in obtaining the necessary objects and tools, or is given a prefabricated semi-finished object. The student will be able to visualize the physical process and visualize the object needed for modeling, imagining it and creating its appearance on the computer.

This process is an important step in the formation of the student's imagination. In particular, the ability to move from a particular physical phenomenon to its model can be the basis for developing a student's sense of research.

It is also possible to assign a student the task of researching a ready-made model based on his / her knowledge potential. The student independently studies the physical process in the model, draws appropriate conclusions and presents the results to the teacher in the form of a report.

Nowadays, design assignments are very popular in many universities. The project method is a new calculation in world pedagogy. It originated in the United States over the last century. It is also called the problem method. Organizing students' independent work using

the project method and the Interactive physics simulator, in our opinion, leads to the effectiveness of the educational process.

The design method always allows students to model and research a physical process over a period of time, or to present a pre-designed computer model based on individual, pair, or group activities. When using the project method, special attention should be paid to the structure of the project, whether it is a complex or a simple task:

1. Attention should be paid to the distribution of the project topic by the level of knowledge of the students participating in the project.
2. The teacher should provide questions, comments, recommendations, video tutorials and other methodological assistance to the students participating in the project.
3. It is advisable for the teacher to report the results on the scheduled days and to encourage the group to discuss them with the participants.
4. It is advisable to keep in touch with project participants through forums, chats or various types of messaging (mailAgentb Skype, QIP), which are elements of communication on the Internet.

Students' independent work can also be organized through laboratory work with game elements. Below is a game model based on Interactive physics (Slanted Coordinate Axis) (Figure)

Keywords: Coordinates, inclined x and y arrows, point coordinates

Objective: To develop students' ability to identify coordinate points.

Student: Determines the coordinates of the target, tries to damage them.

Instructor: Informs students that choosing the right coordinate axis direction and coordinate head will make it easier to solve a particular problem.

The main task of laboratory work with game elements is to measure or observe the values of physical quantities using the laws of physics. However, the computer allows you to turn such measurements into the necessary steps to win the game. Elements of the game increase students' interest in reading, while at the same time helping them to better understand and master the material. The student is given the following tasks: to hit a target, to catch something, to cross a given path in a very short time, and so on. Apparently, this

activity has a number of advantages over traditional laboratory work. On the other hand, such work requires extra time and good preparation of students.

The following models are based on the Interactive Physics application environment and cover the mechanics of physics. These models can be used in general physics, secondary special education, as well as in the teaching of physics and mechanics in higher education.

These models begin with keywords for each physical phenomenon under consideration. Then there is the general interface of the model, the general purpose of the work. The role of the student and the teacher in working with the model is also included.

The models listed in the appendix can be selected based on the lesson plan. These models can be used as homework for students to study independently, in clubs, or when working with students who are unsatisfactory.

It can also be used in distance learning in virtual labs and design classes. The tables in the appendix show the models created in the Interactive Physics environment for each subject, based on the calendar-subject plans in physics for academic lyceums specializing in specific sciences, respectively. Demonstration experiments from such models can be given as independent work in lectures, physics problem-solving and laboratory classes, seminars, and design classes.

An experimental analysis of the interactive physics simulator for different types of activities to determine the effectiveness of the physics teaching process.

		Save time	Course content delivery guarantee	Easy to accept theme	Opportunity to activate the learning process			Improving the level of independent learning			Distance education
					Interest	Abstract	Scientific	Efficiency	Degree of recon		
Lecture	Using demonstration experiments through models created in IP	+									
	Modeling a physical process										
	Conduct blitz queries using an IP model										
Lab Practical	Pre-created in IP										
	Problem modeling in IP										
	Tracking the case condition in IP										
	Problem solving through an simulator on IP										
Lab work	Creating virtual lab										

	work on IP									
	Working with simulators									
	Prohibition work									
	Perform pre-created virtual lab work on IP									
Computer modeling class	Microprojects in the IP environment									
	Modeling of physical processes in IP									
	Creating simulators									

- + The use of this method forms the specified quality
- The use of this method does not affect the quality
- ± This method has both positive and negative effects on the process under consideration
- ± + pluses are more than minuses
- ± - minuses outweigh pluses

References:

1. К.П. Абдурахманов, В.С.Хамидов, О. Очилова *Физика фанидан лаборатория ишларини бажаришда виртуал конструктордан фойдаланиш.* «Олий таълимда Ахборот-коммуникация технологиялари» Республика илмий-амалий конференцияси, Тошкент 2010 (ТАТУ).
2. В.С. Хамидов. *Interactive physics муҳитида физик жараёнларни моделлаштириш.* Таълимда Ахборот-Коммуникация технологиялари , III-том, Тошкент 2006, : 294-298 б.
3. С.М. Дунин. *Наш необъятный двор... "Компьютер в школе"*, 1999, 1.с.13-14.
4. *О подготовке к применению в школах интерактивной компьютерной среды "Живая Физика"* . "Преподавание физики в высшей школе: Школьная методика". Сб.научных трудов, 1996, 5. : с. 24-27.
5. Е. Гурская *Компьютер для школьника. Домашние задания быстро и просто.* Москва : С-Питербург, 2007. 304 ст.
6. Ф.Б.Турахонов, В.С. Хамидов. *Interactive physics дастурининг имкониятлари ҳақида.* Физика ва астрономия муаммолари. Ўқитиш методикаси. Республика илмий ва илмий-методик конференция материаллари тўплами,ТДПУ: Тошкент, 2010.

